

Renal and Ureteral Stone Treatment by Extracorporeal Shock Wave Lithotripsy

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ABSTRACT

Extracorporeal shock wave lithotripsy (ESWLs) results can be enhanced by the application of specific technological concepts and the selection of advantageous instances. This study's goal is to analyze the mechanisms of action of ESWL., indications and contraindications, success predictors, and consequences. ESWLs & "calculi" were used as topics in a search between Jan. 1984 and Oct. 2013 in the Pubmed® database. Only human-conducted studies with a sufficient level of evidence, including clinical trials or reviews/meta-analyses, were considered for inclusion. To optimize the seek for the ESWL results, many technical factors, including the kind of ESWLs apparatus, the intensity & frequency of the impulses, the connecting of patients to the device, the position of the stones, as well as the type of anesthesia, should be taken into consideration. Other patient-related variables, such as the density & size of the stone, skin-to-stone distance, anatomy of the excretory system, and renal anomalies, are also significant. The insertion of a routine double J stent before the procedure is not typically advised, nor is antibiotic prophylaxis required. For stones larger than 10 mm, alpha-blockers, in particular, tamsulosin, are helpful. Following ESWL, minor problems are possible but often respond favorably to therapeutic therapy. It is unclear how ESWL affects those with diabetes or hypertension.

KEY WORDS: Renal colic, kidney stone, ESWL, ureter stone, lithotripsy.

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INTRODUCTION

One of the most common interventions options is extracorporeal shock wave lithotripsy (ESWLs) which is used in the treatment of from ureteral &/or renal stone, it was brought into clinical practice during the 1980s. Notwithstanding, its applicability have been reduced because of the advancement of endourology & minimally-invasive surgery and those procedures' excellent success rates. From that point on, it has become important to look for the ideal specialized boundaries and cautious determination of contender for ESWL to advance its outcomes and legitimize its usage. This study is designed to review the way that ESWL acts, indications of its use and its contraindications, prescient variables for progress, & its complications (early and late complications). [1]

TECHNICAL TENETS

ESWLs involves shattering of the stone using pulsed acoustic waves that are aimed at the stone from an external source of power known as a lithotripter. These waves are high intensity and low frequency. Numerous technical factors, including device manufacturer [2], the energy content, the impulses frequency, the degree of coupling between the patients & ESWLs device, point of focus, stones location, & the type of anesthesia, must be taken into account in order to optimize the results of ESWL.

Each pulse should begin with a low level of energy (13–14 KV) and then gradually increase in energy [3]. As a result of the consecutive shock waves, formation of cavitation bubbles surrounding the stone as well as direct shearing forces are applied to it. As these bubbles break, energy is released which accelerates stones' disintegration [4]. Currently, rates between (60 and 90) shock/min. was used, enhancing stone fragmentation and lowering procedure morbidity with a constant increment in energy [5,6].

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According to a recent meta-analysis, ESWLs with a rate of 60 compared to 120 pulses per minute was more effective [5]. And as Abood *et al.* demonstrated [7], this improvement is most obvious in calculi exceeding 10 mm.

The success of ESWL is increased by the proper connection of patients to lithotripsy machines. The efficiency of shock waves is negatively related to the amount of air in their passage [8-10]. In order to maximize the delivery of shock waves, the focal zone has also been studied. According to recommended guidelines, ureteral calculi should be treated with a focus zone (28 x 6 mm) and renal stones with a larger one (50 x 9 mm) [4].

In order to properly evaluate the patient prior operation, non-contrast spiral computed tomography is a preferred examination since it offers the most important data regarding the indication and prognosis [11]. Prior to the surgery, coagulation patterns & urinary cultures should be examined. Normally, the patient is positioned supine, however in cases of pelvic kidney, horseshoe kidney, or

distal ureter calculi, shifting to a ventral posture creates a better "window" that is clear of the iliac crest. Either fluoroscopy or ultrasonography are used to identify the calculus depending on its size, density, and location. With the latter method, low density renal and ureteral stones can be more accurately identified without the use of ionizing radiation.

Since the effectiveness of ESWLs depends on the exact location of the calculus, a good option for ESWLs is to reduce breathing movements by high frequency ventilation and low current volume [12,13]. Fluoroscopy-based automated tracking devices or expanding the focal zone both aid in the proper shock wave delivery to the calculus [4]. The treatment can start following sedation or general anesthesia, which is favored because of improved results [14]. Approximately 3,000 pulses are used in the majority of services, and the entire treatment takes about an hour.

The technical parameters that have an impact on the ESWL outcomes are included in **Table (1)** together with their corresponding evidence levels and recommendation grades.

Factor	Evidence	Study type	Level of evidence	Grade of recommendation	Authors
Lithotripsy device	There is no difference between lithotripters (electrohydraulic, electromagnetic or piezoelectric) in the treatment of kidney stones	Case control	III	B	Alanee S
Energy	Start with low energy and increase gradually	Prospective, randomized	1b	A	Lambert EH
Frequency of pulses	A lower frequency (60Hz) performs better than the high frequency (120Hz)	Meta-analysis of randomized clinical studies	1a	A	Li K
Coupling	The presence of air in the path of the shock wave negatively affects the results of ESWL	<i>In vitro</i> study/Series of cases	III	B	Pishchalnikov YA and Jain A /Li G
Location of the calculus	Kidney movements during respiration negatively affect ESWL. High frequency ventilation can optimize the results	Retrospective cohort study	III	B	Warner MA and Cormack JR
Anesthesia	General anesthesia shows better results than sedation	Retrospective cohort study	III	B	Sorensen C

INDICATIONS

With a rate of success of 33 to 91%, ESWL is currently regarded as the primary intervention for renal calculi < 2.0 cm. Use of Lithotripsy in the treatment of stones larger than 2 cm has already been documented in several series, however, the low success rates and need for numerous sessions to improve results are limiting factors [15]. Because of how minimally invasive treatment is, ESWL is also suggested for use with ureteral stone [16]. According to a recently meta-analysis, the overall stone-free percentage following emergency Lithotripsy for ureteral calculi is 78% (75% - 82%), with rates of 79 % (61% - 95%) for proximal ureteral stone, 78% (69% - 88%) for mid ureteral stone, & 79% (74% - 84%) for distal ureteral stone [17].

CONTRAINDICATION OF ESWL

Pregnancy, untreated urosepsis or UTI, decompensated coagulopathy, uncontrollable tachyarrhythmia, & abdominal aortic aneurysms larger than 4 cm are an official contraindications to ESWL [18]. Alternative treatments should be suggested if any of these symptoms are present.

PREDICTORS OF SUCCESS

A number of variables, including the calculus' size, location, composition, density, calyceal diverticula, horseshoe kidney, ectopic kidney/renal fusion, obstruction/stasis, stenosis of the ureteropelvic junction, hydronephrosis, and patient-related variables, can affect the outcome of ESWL (renal failure, obesity, skin to stone distance).

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Result is presented by ESWL in an inverse relationship to calculus size. ESWLs does have a rate of success of (33, 56, & 74) % for renal calculi greater than 2 cm , 2 cm , & up to 1 cm respectively, according to meta-analysis by Lingeman *et al.* [15] which conducted in 1994.

Numerous articles looking at ESWL success predictors have been published. In a retrospective study including 427 participants undergoing ESWL for stone size up to 3 cm, Al-Ansari *et al.* [19] reported a success rate about (78 %) after 3 months. However, More than 1 session was necessary for 53.1% of these individuals, & 8.4% have their therapy supplemented with different method (percutaneous nephrolithotomy, flexible ureteroscopy or double-J stenting). The number, size, and location of calculi, in addition to renal anastomosis and congenital abnormalities, all had an effect on the success rate in this sample of patients. 90% of calculations less than ten mm were successful, while 70% of calculations greater than ten mm did so ($p < 0.05$). The success rate for calculi in the upper pole and renal pelvis was 87.3 and 88.5%, respectively, but the success rate for calculi in the lower pole were 69.5% ($p < 0.05$). A solitary kidney stone have a 78.3% success rate, but many kidney calculi had a 62.8% success rate ($p < 0.01$). The success rate for kidneys without dilatation was 83%, however, 76% of kidneys stone with hydronephrosis were successful ($p < 0.05$). Compared to congenital kidneys defects, which have a success rate of 54%, patients without abnormalities had a rate of success of 79% ($p < 0.03$).

In a broader analysis of 2,954 patients who underwent ESWL for calculi smaller than 3 cm, treatment with lithotripsy demonstrated a 86.7% stone-free rate after a three months follow-up. Size, position, stones quantity, congenital abnormalities, & renal anatomy were all reliable indicators of succeed, according to a logistic regression analysis.

The features of the calculus as well as the patient have been examined in certain research. Perks *et al.* [20] revealed 40%

stone-free rate & 24 % full fragmentation in a retrospective study involving 111 patients with calculi < 2.0 cm who had ESWL. Stone composition, size, location, body mass index, attenuation, & skin-to-stone distance (SSD) were all included in the multivariate analysis. The results revealed that these variables are significantly and independently related to the outcomes of complete fragmentation.

Wiesenthal *et al.* [21] investigated 422 participant having kidney or ureter stone sizing 2 cm or less through an effort to develop a therapeutic nomogram to predict the effectiveness of Lithotripsy in the treatment of kidney & ureter stone. In a 3-month follow-up, the rate of success with one ESWL session is 70.2% for renal calculi & 60.3% in case of ureter stone, respectively. With regard to ureteral calculi, BMI & the size of the stone are indicators to ESWL successful in logistic regression. In a separate investigation, Kanao *et al.* [22] examined (435) individuals who had kidney & ureter stone & created a nomogram that included position, size (renal pelvis vs. renal calyx vs. proximal vs. distal ureter), & stone number into account as an indicator of successfulness. Proximal ureter stone up to 5 mm had the best success rate (93.8%), while numerous calcine calculi more than 21 mm had the lowest success rate (10.5%).

There are few ongoing studies examining the lithotripsy in renal urinary stone success predictors. A three-month computed tomography follow-up for 120 patients having kidney stone size (0.5 - 2.5) cm who underwent lithotripsy revealed positive outcomes, 87.5% of individuals are stone free or having residual stone up to 4 mm. In a study of multivariate analysis revealed that the BMI ($p = 0.04$) & densities of the stones more than 1000 Hounsfield units ($p = 0.02$) are indicators of successfulness [11].

It is still debatable whether ESWL is appropriate for lower calyx calculi, because renal anatomy—specifically, the infundibular calicinal angle, infundibular length, width, and height—can have a detrimental effect [23-25].

Table 2. lists the primary contributing causes to a poor prognosis for the success of ESWL along with the evidence and recommendation.

Factor	Evidence	Study type	Level of evidence	Grade of recommendation	Authors
Size of the calculus	Size is inversely proportional to the ESWL result	Meta-analysis of cohort studies	Ila	B	Lingeman JE
calculus density	High density calculi present worse results (>1000 LH)	Prospective cohort study	Iib	B	El-Nahas AR
Location of the calculus	Lower pole renal calculi present worse results than mid-pole and upper pole calculi. Calcine calculi have worse outcomes compared to renal pelvic and ureteral stones.	Retrospective cohort study	III	B	Al Ansari A and Kanao K
Skin-to-stone distance	Distances over 9 cm negatively affect ESWL	Retrospective cohort study	III	B	Perks AJ and Wiesenthal JD
Anatomy of the excretory path	Unfavorable anatomy (infundibulopelvic angle <90°, infundibular length > 3.0 cm and infundibular width of <4.5 mm) negatively affect ESWL	Retrospective cohort study	III	B	Elbahnsy
Kidney anomalies	Kidneys with congenital anomalies have lower elimination rates	Retrospective cohort study	III	B	Al Ansari A

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ADJUVANT ELEMENTS FOR ESWL

Antibacterial are not required with Lithotripsy for individuals having sterile urine. The prevalence of fever or urine infection was not decreased by antibiotic prophylaxis, according to meta-analysis of 9 studies including 1,364 individuals.

Routine double-J stenting before Lithotripsy would not raise percentage of individuals who are stone-free or with lower complications, hence it should not be promoted. The operation without a ureteral catheter is possible even in patients with one kidney, although careful candidate selection is necessary [26]. A systematic review [27] that examined the outcomes and risks of ESWL in the treatment of upper urinary tract calculi with or without double-J stenting prior to the intervention evaluated the sources including the PubMed®, Embase®, and Cochrane databases. The rate of stone-free response, steinstrasse, hematuria, symptoms of the lower urinary tract, infection, discomfort, fever, vomiting, & nausea, as well as requirement of analgesics & adjuvant intervention for the removal of the stone, were all examined. A randomized 8 studies with 876 participants subdivided into 453 catheterized individuals and 423 catheter-free patients were found. The meta-findings analysis's revealed no discernible difference between the groups. With the exception of one research, incidence of steinstrasse was comparable between both groups (with & without catheter). However, patients who had a catheter had a significantly greater prevalence of lower urinary tract signs.

There is strong evidence that alpha-blocker medication therapy, particularly tamsulosin, has advantages for post-ESWL care. Tamsulosin has been shown to be truly effective in patients undergoing ESWL according to a recent meta-analysis, which found that the medicine raises average stone eradication rates about 16% (5–27%) & reduces average stone eradication times about 8 (3–20) days. As a supplement to ESWL treatment, other drugs like nifedipine have also shown promise, although they come with a high risk of adverse effects like hypotension and dizziness [28].

COMPLICATIONS

After ESWL, a number of minor problems may arise. Analgesics are required in up to 40% of patients due to the prevalence of flank pain, presence of petechiae or subcutaneous bruises in the entry & departure site of the waves, and these symptoms. Nearly all patients have microscopic hematuria, while only around one-third of patients have extensive hematuria [29]. The most frequent complications were renal colic (40%), gross hematuria (32%), urinary obstruction (30.9%), and perirenal hematoma or subclinical subcapsular hematoma (4.6%), according to a prospective analysis including 3,241 individual having stone bigger than 4 mm who underwent lithotripsy (7,245 sessions). Additionally, in 9.7% of instances, bacteriuria with symptoms was identified. Most of the time, pain

patients can be properly treated with anti-inflammatory &/or anti-spasmodic medications without the need for additional interventions such recurrent ESWL or ureteroscopies.

Patients with gross hematuria show spontaneous recovery in 85% of instances after 48 hours and in practically 100% of cases within 10 days [30]. Up on size, quantity, & location of the stone, patients with urinary blockage may be treated either medically by alpha-blockers or with surgery by ureteroscopy or double-J stenting. When perirenal hematomas are substantial in size, imaging tests and hemoglobin and hematocrit control should be used to monitor them. There have only been a few reports of post lithotripsy renal explosion documented, & yet in those situations, conservative therapy could be necessary. Intraoperative hypertension & utilization of antiplatelet/anticoagulant medication were found to be significant risks factor that could cause perirenal hematoma as reported by a study including 6,172 lithotripsy sessions by Razvi *et al.* [31].

A number of papers have attempted to show a connection between Lithotripsy and the onset of diabetes and hypertension in relationship to late complications. Chew *et al.* [32] didn't discover a high prevalence of those disorders in a research grouping in comparison with population mean in a retrospective evaluation including 727 individuals having ESWL. Krambeck *et al.* [33] as well discovered no connection between Lithotripsy & high blood pressure in both univariate & multivariate analyses, involving gender, age, & obesity in a study including 4,782 participants having kidney stones without hypertension followed by an average of 8.7 years. However, in a study that gathered prospective data via a questionnaire being sent and answered by 2,041 patients undergoing ESWL, B arbosa *et al.* [34] found a significant yet slight increase in the incidence of elevated blood pressure in such patients in comparison with controls matched by gender, age, & BMI.

In a research that was identical to the one stated above that included 1,869 participants who underwent lithotripsy, it was not discovered that these individuals had a greater prevalence of diabetes than controls who were comparable for gender, age, & BMI. In both univariate and multivariate analysis, involving gender, age, & obesity, a study including 5,287 individuals having stone but not diabetic who were followed for a mean of 8.7 yrs. observe no correlation between lithotripsy & the onset of diabetes [35]. Studies with high levels of evidence are required to confirm or disprove the relationship between lithotripsy & the onset of chronic diseases (such as hypertension and diabetes). Last but not least, in regards to a potential worsening of renal function after lithotripsy, El-Assmy *et al.* [36] observe no changes in creatinine levels in a study of 156 patients with a single kidney who underwent ESWL and an average follow-up of 3.8 years, illustrating the safety of this method at least in the medium term.

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CONCLUSION

When treating ureteral calculi, ESWL is an alternate to ureteroscopy and has good outcomes for renal stones size up to 2 cm. The optimization of outcomes depends on a number of technical parameters, and the likelihood of success is influenced by the patient as well as the stone's characteristics, including size, density, skin-to-stone distance, excretory system anatomy, and renal abnormalities. It is not necessary to put a double J stent or administer antibiotic prophylaxis before the treatment. Success rates could rise with alpha-blockers. While late complications have not yet been proved, early and significant complications are uncommon.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declared that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper and declare that they have no known competing financial interests OR non-financial interests, OR personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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